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THE CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE COLOR AND CONSISTENCY OF SECRETIONS FROM THE UPPER AND LOWER RESPIRATORY TRACT IN ASSESSING THE BACTERIAL OR VIRAL ETIOLOGY OF THE DISEASE

Summary. This article presents the results of a comprehensive study aimed at evaluating the diagnostic significance of the macroscopic characteristics of nasal discharge in children with upper respiratory tract infections (URTIs). The goal was to assist in differential diagnosis between bacterial and viral causes. The study analyzed clinical data from 187 children aged 2 to 14 years who presented with symptoms of URTIs. The assessment of nasal secretion types was based on medical history, physical examination, visual inspection of the nasal discharge, and follow-up clinical observation. The discharges were categorized into serous, mucous, sero-mucous, mucopurulent, purulent, and hemorrhagic types. Mucous (25.7%), serous (11.2%), and sero-mucous (9.6%) types were predominantly associated with viral infections, while mucopurulent (24.1%) and purulent (15%) types were significantly associated with bacterial infections, confirmed through positive group A streptococcal rapid antigen tests and/or elevated levels of C-reactive protein (CRP). A single case of hemorrhagic discharge (0.5%) was most likely due to mechanical trauma of the nasal mucosa. The majority of cases (56.1%) occurred in school-aged children (6–12 years). Overall, 78.1% of cases were acute respiratory infections, and 86.1% of patients had fever. Influenza was confirmed in 33.7% of cases. Bacterial infections were effectively managed using antibiotics, primarily amoxicillin, while viral infections responded well to symptomatic treatment. Visual examination of nasal discharge was found to be a practical, low-cost, and accessible tool for initial diagnostic assessment. The study recommends integrating a standardized visual discharge scale into routine clinical practice, supported by digital tools for documentation and analysis. This combined approach enhances diagnostic precision, improves treatment planning, and contributes to rational antibiotic use, which is essential for combating antimicrobial resistance in pediatric populations.

Keywords: respiratory tract secretions, pediatric infections, bacterial etiology, viral etiology, secretion, amoxicillin, C-reactive protein, group A streptococcus, visual diagnostic tools, antibiotic resistance, primary care diagnostics.

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КЛІНІЧНЕ ТА ДІАГНОСТИЧНЕ ЗНАЧЕННЯ КОЛЬОРУ ТА КОНСИСТЕНЦІЇ ВИДІЛЕНЬ З ВЕРХНІХ ТА НИЖНІХ ДИХАЛЬНИХ ШЛЯХІВ ПРИ ОЦІНЦІ БАКТЕРІАЛЬНОЇ АБО ВІРУСНОЇ ЕТІОЛОГІЇ ЗАХВОРЮВАННЯ

Анотація. У статті представлено результати дослідження, спрямованого на визначення діагностичної цінності макроскопічних характеристик назальних виділень у дітей з інфекціями верхніх дихальних шляхів (ВДШ) з метою проведення диференціальної діагностики між вірусною та бактеріальною природою захворювань. У роботі проаналізовано клінічні дані 187 дітей віком від 2 до 14 років, які звернулися по медичну допомогу з ознаками інфекцій ВДШ. Тип назального секрету визначався на основі даних анамнезу, фізикального обстеження, візуальної оцінки та подальшого динамічного клінічного спостереження. Виділення класифікувались як серозні, слизові, серозно-слизові, мукопурулентні, пурулентні або геморагічні. Встановлено, що слизові (25,7%), серозні (11,2%) та серозно-слизові (9,6%) виділення переважно відповідали вірусній етіології захворювання, тоді як мукопурулентні (24,1%) та пурулентні (15%) вказували на бактеріальні інфекції, які були підтверджені результатами експрес-тестів на β -гемолітичний стрептокок групи А та/або високим рівнем С-реактивного білка (CRP). Один зареєстрований випадок геморагічного виділення (0,5%) ймовірно був пов'язаний із травматизацією слизової оболонки носа. У більшості випадків (56,1%) пацієнти належали до шкільного віку (6–12 років). Гострі респіраторні інфекції складала 78,1% усіх випадків, а у 86,1% хворих реєструвалася лихоманка. Грип було діагностовано у 33,7% дітей. Бактеріальні інфекції лікувались із застосуванням антибіотиків, зокрема амоксициліну, що продемонстрував ефективність, тоді як при вірусних захворюваннях доцільною була симптоматична терапія. Встановлено, що візуальна оцінка характеру носових виділень є важливим допоміжним критерієм при формулюванні первинного діагнозу. Запропоновано впровадження стандартизованої шкали виділень у клінічну практику як орієнтир при виборі діагностичної та терапевтичної

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тактики. Крім того, підкреслено важливість використання цифрових інструментів для документування й аналізу клінічних даних, що дозволяє підвищити точність діагностики, оптимізувати маршрутизацію пацієнтів, уникнути необґрунтованого призначення антибіотиків і, відповідно, знизити ризик розвитку антибіотикорезистентності.

Ключові слова: респіраторні виділення, педіатричні інфекції, бактеріальна етіологія, вірусна етіологія, виділення, амоксицилін, С-реактивний білок, стрептокок групи А, візуальні діагностичні інструменти, антибіотикорезистентність, діагностика в первинній медичній допомозі.

Relevance. Diseases of the upper and lower respiratory tracts, including acute respiratory viral infections, bacterial sinusitis, tracheitis, bronchitis, and pneumonia, are among the leading causes for patients seeking medical assistance, especially during the autumn-winter period. This may be due to the activation of autoflora under the influence of unfavorable factors or colonization by pathogenic microorganisms. [2, 7] The high incidence of disease in children is contributed by limited immunity acquisition to many pathogens, the spread of social contacts with age, and insufficient personal hygiene skills. Over 200 viruses can cause respiratory system diseases, which account for approximately 90% of all cases. Only 10% of these diseases are caused by bacteria, mycoplasmas, fungi, protozoa, and possible co-infections [6]. Very often, the clinical picture is not specific, making diagnosis and treatment tactics difficult. The inappropriate prescription of antibacterial therapy is one of the causes of the development of antibiotic resistance, which is one of the most dangerous threats of the 21st century. [14] However, in practical medicine, especially at the primary healthcare level, there is often a lack of rapid laboratory methods for confirming the etiology of infections, forcing clinicians to rely on clinical and subjectively available diagnostic markers. One such criterion traditionally used in clinical practice is the assessment of the nature of secretions from the nasal cavity, the posterior pharyngeal wall, trachea, and bronchial tree. A visual analysis of the color, consistency, and quantity of secretions can provide the doctor with preliminary information about the type of pathogen. Studying the nature, composition, and physicochemical properties of respiratory secretions is important for diagnosing and monitoring respiratory diseases of both infectious and non-infectious origin. The secretion formed in the upper (nasal cavity, nasopharynx) and lower (trachea, bronchi, alveoli) respiratory tracts is not only a physiological protective barrier substance but also a diagnostic feature that reflects the condition of the mucous membrane, immune response, and microbial landscape of the respiratory tracts. Depending on the physical characteristics (color, density, transparency), composition, and origin, several main types of secretion are distinguished: mucous, mucopurulent, purulent, serous, and hemorrhagic – similar to the classification proposed by Murray, M. P., Pentland, J. L., Turnbull, K., MacQuarrie, S., & Hill, A. T. (2009). [12] Their differentiation is a very important aspect for determining the etiology of the process, the stage of the disease, and the choice of therapeutic tactics. Mucous secretion is usually transparent or whitish, has an elastic, viscous consistency, and a faint or absent odor. Mucopurulent secretion is characterized by a turbid,

yellowish or light green color, medium viscosity, and reduced transparency. Purulent secretion usually has a pronounced yellow-green or dark green color, a thick consistency, and is often accompanied by an unpleasant odor. This type of secretion is typical of purulent sinusitis, bronchiectasis, lung abscesses, and chronic bacterial bronchitis. Serous secretion is a liquid, watery, transparent or slightly yellowish. This secretion predominates in the early stages of viral infection, allergic rhinitis, or hay fever. Hemorrhagic or bloody secretion contains erythrocytes or their decomposition products, such as hemosiderin, and can be caused by various factors. These include mechanical trauma to the mucous membrane, ulcerative or necrotic processes, neoplasms, tuberculosis, increased vascular permeability, or stagnation in the small circle of circulation. Such secretion may have a pink, red, dark brown, or "rusty" tint, indicating the age or intensity of the hemorrhagic component. The color and consistency of secretion are closely related to its cellular and biochemical composition. The green color is due to a high concentration of myeloperoxidase, an antimicrobial enzyme produced by neutrophils during active purulent inflammation. Brown or reddish secretion is associated with the presence of erythrocytes or their decomposition products, a sign of bleeding or stagnation. The consistency of secretion also depends on the content of mucin, the amount of cellular detritus, pus, and protein molecules. Mucous secretion has a more liquid structure due to the predominance of mucin MUC5AC, while purulent secretion is thick due to the large amount of DNA from dead neutrophils and inflammatory proteins. Secretions from the nasal cavity and bronchial tree have their specific features related to the location and type of epithelium. For example, nasal secretion in allergic rhinitis is usually transparent and watery, whereas in purulent sinusitis, it becomes thick with a yellow-green tint. In turn, sputum from the lower respiratory tracts can be mucopurulent or purulent in bronchitis or pneumonia. Thus, the characterization of secretion is not only an auxiliary clinical parameter but also a potentially important non-invasive indicator of the etiology of the pathological process. Standardizing the approach to assessing the color, consistency, and composition of respiratory secretions will enhance the effectiveness of early diagnosis and clinical management of patients with acute respiratory diseases.

Materials and Methods. A comprehensive approach was used for the study, which included clinical observations, medical history analysis, laboratory tests, and a review of scientific literature. The main material for the research consisted of patients under the age of 18 who sought treatment at an outpatient clinic with symptoms of

respiratory tract diseases. Patients were selected based on the following inclusion criteria: presence of nasal discharge or sputum, suspicion of bacterial or viral etiology of the respiratory disease, and the absence of chronic diseases that could influence the results. The medical history criteria included the duration of the illness, presence of allergic reactions or contact with allergens, as well as factors that could indicate bacterial or viral infection, such as contact with infected individuals, fever, and the nature of symptoms. A clinical examination of the patients was conducted at the outpatient clinic. Symptoms such as changes in the nature and quantity of secretions, temperature, and cough were recorded in the patients' medical records. To differentiate between bacterial and viral etiology of the diseases, some patients underwent a complete blood count, including a white blood cell and eosinophil count. Additionally, to clarify the nature of the inflammatory process, C-reactive protein (CRP) tests and bacterial cultures to detect streptococcus were performed. Macroscopic analysis of the secretion, including the assessment of color, consistency, and odor, was also carried out. The types of secretions considered included mucous, mucopurulent, purulent, serous, and hemorrhagic, with characteristics of consistency, color, and odor. For the scientific part of the study, international databases such as PubMed, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Google Scholar, and other medical resources were used to collect up-to-date information on the mechanisms of formation of different types of respiratory tract secretions and their significance in bacterial and viral infections. Search queries included keywords such as "mucopurulent secretion respiratory tract," "purulent secretion bacterial infection," "mucous secretion viral infections," "nasal discharge color consistency bacterial viral differentiation," "CRP bacterial viral respiratory tract infections," "C-reactive protein in respiratory infections," "clinical significance of nasal secretions in respiratory diseases," "differential diagnosis nasal discharge bacterial viral," "children respiratory tract infections secretion types."

Aim of the study. To determine the clinical and diagnostic significance of the color and consistency of secretions in the upper and lower respiratory tracts in assessing the bacterial or viral etiology of respiratory diseases. To explore the possible correlation between the characteristics of the secretion (color, consistency) and the etiology of respiratory infections, which will allow for the improvement of diagnostic methods and therapy tactics based on macroscopic signs of the secretion.

Results. In the conducted study, data from 187 children aged from 1 month to 18 years who sought primary medical care at the outpatient department of a healthcare institution were analyzed. To ensure a high-quality analysis, the patient sample was stratified by age groups according to the stages of postnatal development and by gender. This approach allowed for a structured assessment of the population characteristics of the pediatric cohort seeking medical assistance.

The group of children under one year of age (from 1 to 12 months inclusive) comprised 35 individuals (18.7% of the total number). Children aged 1 to 3 years (early childhood) accounted for 25 individuals

(13.4%), while the preschool group (3–6 years) also included 25 individuals (13.4%). The largest category was the school-age group (6–12 years) with 80 individuals (42.8%). The adolescent group (12–18 years) included 22 individuals (11.8%). In terms of gender, boys predominated – 105 individuals (56.1%), while girls were 82 (43.9%), indicating a slight but noticeable gender disparity in the frequency of medical consultations.

Nosological Aspects: A structural analysis of morbidity within the pediatric population seeking medical care at the outpatient facility for signs of infectious processes was conducted. Among the clinical nosologies, upper respiratory tract infections, influenza, and infections with high fever were the main contributors to the infectious disease burden in pediatric practice.

Upper respiratory tract infections were diagnosed in 146 children, accounting for 78.1% of the total sample. This figure is expectedly high, as respiratory viral infections remain the leading cause of medical consultations among children of different ages, as reflected in the work of Bohutskaia N.K. [6]. This category included clinical cases of rhinitis, pharyngitis, tonsillitis, laryngitis, and tracheitis, which were usually of viral etiology. In most cases, the course of the illness was relatively mild, although some patients exhibited a subfebrile temperature or a rise in body temperature, requiring differential diagnosis with bacterial infections.

Influenza was detected in 63 children (33.7%), indicating high circulation of the influenza virus during the study period. In some patients, influenza had a typical course with a sudden onset, high fever, headache, pronounced malaise, and upper respiratory tract involvement. The presence of influenza cases with clinically significant symptoms of intoxication emphasizes the need for systematic monitoring of the spread of this infection among the pediatric population, considering the risk of complications and the rapid spread of the virus in organized groups [4].

Infections with high fever were observed in 161 children, accounting for 86.1% of the sample. This figure encompasses a wide range of infections accompanied by significant febrile responses, regardless of whether the etiology was viral or bacterial [4]. The presence of high body temperature (above 38.5°C) required special clinical attention, particularly in terms of ruling out complications such as pneumonia, otitis, tonsillitis with a purulent component, or viral infections with generalized manifestations. The high frequency of such cases also suggests that most patients presented in the acute phase of the disease, aligning with the "early consultation" behavior of parents.

Urinary tract infections were registered in 3 children (1.6% of the sample), and gastroenteritis and enteritis in 7 children (3.7%). Since these patients were not relevant to the study, they were excluded from further analysis.

A separate group consisted of 24 children (12.8%) with multiple infectious diagnoses. In these cases, combinations of upper respiratory tract infections with influenza or influenza with other diseases accompanied by high fever were predominant. The presence of prolonged fever or a recurrent

wave of temperature response most likely indicated reinfection or superimposition of a bacterial infection, complicating the clinical picture and requiring increased caution in managing these patients.

In the analysis of secretions from the upper (nose, nasopharynx) and lower (bronchial tree) respiratory tracts, six main types of secretion were identified according to the classification by Murray, M.P., Pentland, J.L., Turnbull, K., MacQuarrie, S., & Hill, A.T. (2009): mucopurulent, purulent, mucous, serous, serosanguinous, and mucosanguinous, as shown in Table 1 and Figure 1. The type of secretion was determined based on clinical observations, physical examination, and parental reports, allowing for the establishment of a link between the nature of the discharge and the stage of the disease.

The most common type was mucopurulent discharge, observed in 45 children (24.1%). Among them, there were 23 boys (51.1%) and 22 girls (48.9%). This discharge had a yellowish color, sometimes with green or brownish tints, medium thickness, and a mucopurulent consistency. Parents noted that mucopurulent discharge often appeared during coughing and also came from the nose or nasopharynx.

Mucous discharge occurred with a frequency comparable to serous forms and was detected in 48 children (25.7%), of which 25 were boys (52.1%) and 23 were girls (47.9%). The discharge had a whitish or slightly milky color, a mucous consistency, and primarily came from the nose.

Seromucous discharge, which had a transitional consistency from watery to mucous, also ranked high in frequency. It was recorded in 18 children (9.6%), evenly distributed between boys and girls (9 and 9,

respectively). The discharge changed according to the course of the illness, from transparent or pale to milky or white. It mainly came from the nose, and less frequently from the bronchial tree.

Purulent discharge, although similar in nature to mucopurulent, was observed less frequently – in 28 children (15%), among which 15 were boys (53.6%) and 13 were girls (46.4%). This type of discharge was noted for its thick consistency, greenish color, and purulent structure. It came from the nose or nasopharynx.

Serous discharge, transparent or slightly pale, was found in 21 children (11.2%), of which 10 were boys (47.6%) and 11 were girls (52.4%). Its consistency was watery, without purulent inclusions. This type of discharge usually came from the nose and was considered a marker of a mild illness or the early stage of recovery.

The rarest type was mucosanguineous discharge, observed in only one child (0.5%). It had a mucous consistency with streaks or inclusions of blood, indicating damage to the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract or microhemorrhages.

The etiological diagnosis for each type of secretion was conducted using various methods, including a throat swab for group A streptococcus or blood tests, particularly for C-reactive protein (CRP), to differentiate between bacterial and viral infections, as shown in Table 2. It was established that the most common type was mucopurulent discharge, observed in 45 children (24.1%). In most cases, the etiology of mucopurulent discharge was bacterial. To diagnose bacterial inflammation, a throat swab for group A streptococcus was performed. In cases of a negative streptococcus test, additional blood tests, including CRP, were conducted to confirm the bacterial infection. Such nasal or nasopharyngeal

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of a child with nasal discharge, surrounded by six types of nasal/respiratory secretions for educational use in a scientific context.

Source: Created by ChatGPT

Table 1

Distribution of Respiratory Secretions Among Children with Acute Respiratory Infections

Type of Secretion	Total Number of Children	Boys (n)	Girls (n)	Percentage (%)	Common Source (Nose/Throat/Bronchi)
Mucopurulent	45	23	22	24.1	Nose, Throat, Bronchi
Mucous	48	25	23	25.7	Nose
Serous-Mucous	18	9	9	9.6	Nose, Bronchi
Purulent	28	15	13	15.0	Nose, Throat
Serous	21	10	11	11.2	Nose
Mucous-Hemorrhagic	1	1	0	0.5	Nose, Throat
Total	187	82	105	100	-

discharge, yellowish in color and purulent in consistency, was characteristic of bacterial infections, especially inflammatory processes caused by streptococcus or other bacteria.

Purulent discharge was observed in 28 children (15%). The etiological factor for purulent discharge was also a bacterial infection. Tests showed the presence of group A streptococcus in some children, while in others, bacterial infection was confirmed through blood tests with elevated CRP levels and leukocytes, as noted in the study by Francis, N. A., Gillespie, D., Wootton, M., White, P., Bates, J., Richards, J., Melbye, H., Hood, K., & Butler, C. C. (2020) "CRP elevation was associated with bacterial pathogens" [17]. This type of discharge, with a thick consistency and greenish tint, usually came from the nose or nasopharynx, indicating a significant bacterial inflammatory process [17].

Mucous discharge, observed in 48 children (25.7%), was found to have a viral etiology. Clinical observations confirmed that this type of discharge was characteristic of viral infections of the upper respiratory tract, such as infections caused by rhinovirus. In such cases, additional laboratory tests were not conducted, as the viral etiology was evident from the clinical examination.

Seromucous discharge was found in 18 children (9.6%). In most cases, its etiology was viral. However, in some cases, there was a mixed etiology, with signs of progression from a viral infection to a bacterial one. If a bacterial infection was suspected, an additional blood test for CRP was conducted, which allowed confirming the bacterial nature of the inflammation.

Serous discharge, observed in 21 children (11.2%), also had a viral etiology, typical for mild forms of respiratory viral infections or allergic reactions. This type of discharge, transparent or slightly pale, did not require additional laboratory tests to establish the etiology.

Mucosanguineous discharge, observed in only one child (0.5%), was caused by a viral agent, but the hemorrhages in the discharge were due to mechanical damage to the blood vessels of the mucous membrane of the respiratory tract. This occurred as a result of intense nose blowing, leading to the rupture of small capillaries and the appearance of blood streaks in the discharge.

Treatment. Within the scope of the study conducted in a day hospital setting, an analysis of the therapeutic approaches prescribed for patients with upper and lower respiratory tract diseases was performed based on the etiology of the process, determined by the characteristics of the secretion, clinical picture, objective examination, and available laboratory indicators. The treatment strategy was formed in accordance with current national and international protocols for providing medical care to children with respiratory infections.

Treatment of patients with bacterial etiology of the disease. For patients in whom a bacterial process was diagnosed based on the presence of mucopurulent or purulent secretion, elevated C-reactive protein levels, and/or a positive group A streptococcus test, antibacterial therapy was prescribed. The primary first-line drugs chosen were Amoxicillin and Benzathine Penicillin 5.

Table 2

Etiological Factors of Respiratory Secretion Types and Diagnostic Methods

Secretion	Number of Children	Etiological Factor	How Was Determined
Mucopurulent	45	Bacterial (Streptococcus A or bacterial infection)	Throat swab for Streptococcus A, blood test with C-reactive protein (CRP) for differential diagnosis when Streptococcus A was not found
Purulent	28	Bacterial infection	Throat swab for Streptococcus A, blood test with C-reactive protein (CRP)
Mucous	48	Viral	Clinical signs and symptom observation, no bacterial pathogens found
Serous	21	Viral	Clinical observation, no bacterial pathogens found
Seromucous	18	Viral or Bacterial (transition stage)	Clinical observation and progression of disease
Mucous-Hemorrhagic	1	Viral (mechanical damage)	Result of intense nose blowing causing small capillary rupture

In particular, for patients with acute otitis media, Amoxicillin was prescribed in 100% of cases in accordance with the clinical protocol of the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Pädiatrische Infektiologie e.V. (2019) [16].

For children under 12 years of age and weighing less than 40 kg, Amoxicillin was prescribed at a dose of 250 mg three times a day for 7–10 days. For children over 12 years of age and weighing more than 40 kg, the dose was 500 mg three times a day for the same duration of the course. However, in cases of minimal manifestations of bacterial infection, antibiotics were not prescribed due to the global importance of the issue of antibiotic resistance.

Treatment of patients with viral etiology of the disease. For patients with clinical signs of viral infection of the upper respiratory tract, in whom the predominant secretion was serous, mucous, or seromucous, symptomatic therapy was prescribed. Antibiotics were not used in this group, in line with current recommendations on the rational use of antibiotics. To control body temperature in patients with viral infections, antipyretic drugs were prescribed: paracetamol at a dose of 10–15 mg/kg per dose (but not exceeding 60 mg/kg per day) or ibuprofen at a dose of 5–10 mg/kg per dose (not exceeding 30 mg/kg per day). The dosing schedule for antipyretic drugs was determined individually, with a recommendation to use them if the temperature exceeded 38.5°C.

To ease nasal breathing in patients with rhinitis, nasal sprays or drops for nasal cavity irrigation were prescribed. For young children (up to 2 years old), Xylometazoline in the form of drops was mainly prescribed. For children over 6 years old, it was recommended to rinse the nasal cavity with an isotonic or hypertonic solution of sea water 3–4 times a day in the form of a nasal douche; however, alternative use of nasal drops was also acceptable [4].

In cases of significant nasal congestion that significantly worsened the patient's quality of life, short courses (no more than 5 days) of vasoconstrictor nasal drops or sprays based on oxymetazoline or xylometazoline in the appropriate age dosages were prescribed, with an interval of at least 8–12 hours between applications.

All patients, regardless of the etiology of the disease, were advised to maintain an adequate fluid intake, calculated as at least 60–80 ml/kg body weight per day, which helped to moisturize the mucous membranes and facilitate the clearance of secretions from the respiratory tract, as well as to maintain appropriate fluid management based on temperature and weight using the general formula for fluid therapy in children with fever.

Study Limitations. Since the treatment was carried out in a day hospital setting, long-term observation of patients' condition dynamics and changes in the character of secretions during the course of treatment was not conducted. Therapeutic interventions were based on the initial assessment of the nature of the secretion and other clinical and laboratory indicators at the time of the patient's first visit. Parents were provided with detailed recommendations regarding the regimen of drug administration, criteria for the effectiveness of the

prescribed therapy, and indications for seeking medical attention again if no positive dynamics were observed within 48–72 hours or if the child's condition worsened.

Conclusions. The conducted study of respiratory secretions in 187 children aged from 1 month to 18 years allowed the systematization of important clinical and diagnostic characteristics that can be used by primary care physicians for the preliminary differentiation of bacterial and viral etiology of respiratory diseases. The obtained data demonstrated that mucopurulent (24.1%) and purulent (15%) secretions are predominantly of bacterial origin, which was confirmed by laboratory tests (positive group A streptococcus test and/or elevated C-reactive protein levels). In contrast, mucous (25.7%), serous (11.2%), and serosanguineous (9.6%) secretions are mainly associated with viral infections. The presence of blood in the secretions, recorded in one case (0.5%), was a result of mechanical damage to the mucosal vessels. In the nosological structure of upper respiratory tract infections, they accounted for 78.1% of visits; infections with a high fever were recorded in 86.1% of children; influenza was recorded in a third of the patients (33.7%), and in 12.8% of cases, a combination of several infectious nosologies was observed. Therapeutic analysis showed that antibacterial therapy (mainly amoxicillin) was effective in treating bacterial infections associated with mucopurulent and purulent secretions, while symptomatic therapy (antipyretics, nasal irrigation, vasoconstrictor drugs) was sufficient for treating viral infections with mucous and serous secretions. Such a rational approach to antibiotic therapy depending on the type of secretion allowed optimizing the treatment strategy. It is important to emphasize that visual assessment of secretion characteristics (color, consistency) can serve as a valuable guide for the preliminary differentiation of bacterial and viral etiology of the disease, but it should not be the sole source for determining the etiological factor. The combination of clinical assessment of secretions with laboratory methods (CRP, streptococcus test) increases diagnostic accuracy with further appropriate therapy prescription.

Based on the conducted study, the following recommendations can be proposed for primary care physicians: it is advisable to implement standardized criteria for describing the color and consistency of secretions in daily practice using visual scales and documenting the characteristics of upper and lower respiratory tract secretions in medical documentation. The recommended diagnostic algorithm suggests that in the presence of yellow-green (mucopurulent/purulent) secretions, it is advisable to conduct a rapid test for group A streptococcus and/or determine the level of C-reactive protein to confirm bacterial etiology. When transparent or whitish (serous/mucous) secretions are detected, it is recommended to refrain from prescribing antibiotics and limit the treatment to symptomatic therapy. In cases of mixed-type secretions or the presence of additional risk factors (immunodeficiency, chronic diseases), additional laboratory tests should be performed. Rational antibiotic therapy should be based on

the principle of prescribing antibiotics only when clinical and laboratory signs of bacterial infection are present.

An important aspect is educating patients and parents, including explanations about the differences between bacterial and viral infections, and clarifying that a change in the color of secretions during the illness (from clear to yellowish) is not always an indication for prescribing antibiotics. Dynamic monitoring should include a follow-up examination of patients with mucopurulent secretions 48–72 hours after the initiation of therapy, assessing changes in the characteristics of the secretions during treatment, and in the absence of positive dynamics or worsening of the condition, considering alternative diagnostic and therapeutic strategies.

Regarding further research and implementation, it is proposed to expand diagnostic capabilities by developing a color scale for assessing secretions with photographic examples for standardizing diagnostics, introducing rapid tests for detecting

viral antigens in respiratory secretions, and studying the relationship between the microbiological composition of secretions and their macroscopic characteristics. A multidisciplinary approach should involve the participation of otolaryngologists, pulmonologists, and immunologists in creating a unified protocol for the assessment of secretions and conducting regular interdisciplinary discussions of complex cases with atypical secretion characteristics. The improvement of diagnostics for upper respiratory infections in children is possible through prospective studies that assess the diagnostic value of nasal secretion types, their biochemical and immunological characteristics, as well as the development of a scale that considers age, seasonality, chronic diseases, and epidemiological history. The proposed measures will contribute to improving the accuracy of differential diagnosis of respiratory infections at the primary healthcare level, optimizing antibiotic therapy, and reducing the risk of antibiotic resistance development.

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